

Horizon 2020
Programme

Cost/Benefit analysis

Tool / Technology: GPS collar (Telespor or FindMy)

Analysis prepared by (country): Norway

Production type the tool/technology is relevant for: Dairy / **Meat** / Both

Description of the “benchmark” farm for which the analysis is performed:

Country: Norway

Production type:

Mainly outdoors / Housed 0-3 months a year / **Housed 4-8 months a year** / Mainly indoors

Farm grazing area: 120 ha (10 ha arable land and fenced pasture. Abundant rangeland grazing area for summer grazing.)

Species: **Sheep** / Goat

Number of animals: 80 ewes

Breed: Norwegian white sheep

Number of staff: 1

This project has received funding from
the European Union's Horizon 2020
research and innovation programme
under grant agreement N° 101000471.

Costs

• **Capital costs (e.g. large items):**

€1 - €500 €501- €1,000 €1,001-€2,500 €2,501-€5,000 €5,001-€15,000 > €15,000

• **Individual costs (e.g. per tag, per sample, per collar):**

€1 - €20 €21- €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

• **Leasing costs (if not purchased):**

Annual Monthly Weekly €1 - €50 €51-€200 €201-€500 > €500

• **Infrastructure requirements:**

Decrease Increase No change

• **Power source requirements:**

Not required Mains Battery Solar Other

• **Percentage of animals within the flock/herd that use/are equipped/take advantage of the technology: 20 - 100 %**

• **Subscription fee – Needed? Yes / No**

○ If yes

Per flock / herd <input type="checkbox"/>	Per individual animal <input type="checkbox"/>	Per unit <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
Annual <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Monthly <input type="checkbox"/>	Weekly <input type="checkbox"/>
€1 - €50 <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	€51 - €200 <input type="checkbox"/>	€201 - €500 <input type="checkbox"/>
		Over €500 <input type="checkbox"/>

• **Maintenance / replacement parts:**

Easy to obtain Difficult to obtain Not obtainable Don't know

• **Licences or permits required? Yes / No**

○ If yes, cost:

€1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

• **Training required to install / use? Yes / No**

If yes, time range: Up to an hour Half day Full day More

• **Technical / mechanical support provided on farm, after purchase? Yes / No**

• **Maintenance cost – included in the subscription: Yes / No / Not applicable**

If no, cost per month: €1 - €50 €51 - €200 €201 - €500 Over €500

• **Additional technical advice required (e.g. advisor time)? Yes / No**

Benefits (tick all that apply)

Management

- Labour / time saving
- Accuracy of records (health, management, movements etc.)
- Management decisions for animal groupings
- Better individual animal management
- Improved medicine use
- Better nutrition / meeting requirements better
- Improved use of feed resource (grazing, concentrates, etc.)
- Product quality improvements (e.g. hay, carcass, growth, milk, etc.)
- Increased information on production system
- Opportunity for sharing / moving device (more than one location)

Animal

- Reduced stress to the animal(s)
- Improved welfare of the animals(s)
- Additional information on animal behaviour
- Information on water intake / water availability
- Information on food intake / food availability

Technical

- Compatibility with other devices
- Ease of data transfer to other software
- Easy to use once installed

Other

- Reduced stress to farmer / staff
- Environmental benefits (e.g. reduced wastage, improved biodiversity, etc.)

- Helps to attract new entrants in to the small ruminant industries

Another benefit not listed? Please give details:

Surveillance of animals on unfenced rangeland pastures is a concern in the public opinion as well as for sheep farmers. This tech can improve this situation.

Also land use is under pressure, and documenting the land used for grasing animals is important to document land use needs for farming.

May be the tool that will keep sheep farmers into sheep farming, as well as allowing recruitment of young farmers.

Overall summary:

- **Recommend this tool/technology for this type of benchmark farm?**

Yes / ~~No~~ / ~~Maybe~~

- **Additional comments?**

Annual costs vary depending on coverage. Collars that need to communicate through satalites are more costly than those that communicate through GSM.

